

Interactive High-Performance Visualization for Astronomy and Cosmology

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Abstract—The exponential growth of data in Astrophysics and Cosmology demands scalable computational tools and intuitive interfaces for analysis and visualization. In this work, we present an innovative integration of the VisIVO scientific visualization framework with the InterActive Computing (IAC) service at Cineca, enabling interactive, high-performance visual workflows directly within HPC environments. Through seamless integration into Jupyter-based science gateways, users can now access GPU-enabled compute nodes to perform complex 3D visualizations using VisIVO via custom Python wrappers and preconfigured interactive notebooks. We demonstrate how this infrastructure simplifies access to advanced HPC resources, enhances reproducibility, and accelerates exploratory workflows in astronomical research. Our approach has been validated through a set of representative use cases involving large-scale simulations from the GADGET code, highlighting the effectiveness of this system in visualizing the large-scale structure of the Universe. This work exemplifies how science gateways can bridge domain-specific tools and advanced infrastructures, fostering user-centric, scalable, and reproducible research environments.

Keywords—Science Gateways, Interactive Visualization, High-Performance Computing, VisIVO, Jupyter Notebooks, Astronomy and Cosmology

I. INTRODUCTION

Enormous data volumes, on the scale of petabytes, are produced through astrophysical observations or simulation codes running on high-performance supercomputers. These vast quantities of data create substantial obstacles to storage, retrieval, and analysis, which are crucial in facilitating scientific breakthroughs [1]. Pre-exascale systems provide remarkable possibilities for scaling high-performance computing applications in Astrophysics and Cosmology (A&C), necessitating both superior computational performance and interactive visualization of the results.

VisIVO¹, the Visualization Interface for the Virtual Observatory, is a set of tools designed for analyzing multi-dimensional data and uncovering previously unidentified connections within complex, multi-variate astrophysical datasets. It has been implemented in two ways: (1) through Science Gateways [2] for accessing Distributed Computing Infrastructures (DCIs) such as clusters, grids, and clouds, and (2) by leveraging containerization and virtualization technologies

on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure, integrated into interactive notebook applications [3].

In this study, we discuss the innovative incorporation of VisIVO into the InterActive Computing (IAC²) service [4] provided by the Cineca HPC centre. IAC service allows end users to obtain access to HPC compute nodes via the web browser, replacing the traditional approach to HPC resources which is limited to a command line interface via *ssh* and a queued batch system. Typical usage scenarios for IAC are interactive analyses, visualizations, and steering of simulations running on scalable compute services that abstract large-scale computing resources, which can be used for running highly parallel simulation applications, but are also suitable for data analysis tasks, involving extreme-scale data sets.

The adopted strategy consists of the integration of VisIVO with IAC thus permitting its interactive execution on an HPC cluster (currently Galileo 100³ at Cineca), with the goal of simplifying user engagement with the clusters and fostering reproducibility of the visualization workflows through the developed interactive notebooks.

In conclusion, we present the interactive notebooks developed through various VisIVO workflows, which aid in examining the Universe's large-scale structure. These studies utilize extensive cosmological N-body simulations generated with the GADGET code [5], [6].

II. VISIVO SERVER

VisIVO Server is a suite of software tools designed to create customized 3D visualizations from astrophysical data, supporting large-scale datasets without fixed limits on dimensionality.

Its main modules available via Command Line Interface (CLI) are as follows:

- VisIVO Importer: converts user-supplied datasets into VisIVO Binary Tables (VBT), an efficient internal data representation. It supports various formats, including the general purpose data formats such as ASCII or CSV or tailored astronomical data formats such as FITS, HDF5, GADGET and more.

²IAC, <https://jupyter.g100.cineca.it/>

³Galileo 100 infrastructure: <https://www.hpc.cineca.it/systems/hardware/galileo100/>

¹VisIVO, <https://visivo.readthedocs.io/>

Fig. 1: VisIVO Server modular architecture and basic workflow involving importer, filter and view operations

- VisIVO Filter: processes VBTs to apply data transformations, filtering, and other operations to prepare datasets for visualization.
- VisIVO Viewer: generates interactive 3D visualizations from VBTs, allowing users to explore and analyze their data effectively.

A typical usage of VisIVO Server involves at least three steps for data preparation, processing and visualization (see e.g. Figure 1). For sample VisIVO commands please see Section V-A.

a) Data Preparation: Use VisIVO Importer to convert your dataset into a VBT.

b) Data Processing (Optional): Apply one or more VisIVO Filter operations to perform data transformations or filtering on the VBT as needed.

c) Data Visualization: Utilize one or more VisIVO Viewer renderings to create 3D visualizations from the (processed) VBT.

This modular workflow allows for efficient handling and visualization of complex astrophysical datasets.

III. INTERACTIVE COMPUTING SERVICE (IAC)

The increasing complexity and interactivity of modern scientific research workflows require compute resources that extend beyond traditional batch processing. In response to

this demand, the Fenix⁴ infrastructure introduces InterActive Compute services (IAC) as a core component of its federated service portfolio, targeting the specific needs of the neuroscience community within the Human Brain Project⁵ (HBP) and its successor, EBRAINS⁶. The IAC implementation in Fenix was managed by Cineca and E4 Company on the basis of the ICE4HPC suite⁷ by E4, and it is currently up and running on the Galileo 100 cluster at Cineca.

The main benefits for an interactive approach to HPC resources are mainly two.

- 1) Users can access directly to the compute node of an HPC system using a web browser interface (available at <https://jupyter.g100.cineca.it>). This is a quite far away approach with respect to the traditional user experience on HPC clusters, which traditionally involves *ssh* access to a single shared login node, and a batch system allowing job submissions in a queue system. The traditional approach, relying only on command line, inhibits any graphical visualization of results, which is on the contrary very smooth on the interactive web interface.
- 2) HPC resources are guaranteed in a near-instantaneous access to allow an immediate interaction via web browser. This represents a different philosophy with respect to the above-mentioned batch approach (where the job start time is unpredictable by the user). This approach adds the possibility of an on-the-fly interaction with the workflow while the system is running [7], a real-time monitoring of the resource usage and visualization of the intermediate results to make decisions on the following steps of the workflow.

The general implementation of the service is depicted in Figure 2. The framework is composed of three main parts:

- 1) a frontend virtual machine (VM), which exposes the website to the world wide web (it is not exposed from the cluster login nodes for security reasons). The interface asks for user credentials and Two-Factor authentication, then it shows a form to be filled with drop-down menus to request resources to be allocated on the HPC cluster
- 2) such requested resources are used to submit a job on the cluster on a dedicated partition, as such a VM is able, exceptionally, to communicate directly with the cluster Slurm controller. The job will run a Jupyter-based [8] server instance (detailed later) which is tunneled to the VM to be exposed externally
- 3) the near-istantaneous access is guaranteed since the dedicated Slurm partition (“backend nodes” in Figure 2) is provided in oversubscription, thus, in the unlucky hypothesis of a fully allocated partition, multiple users would share the same CPU. Oversubscription is not

⁴Fenix, <https://fenix-ri.eu/>

⁵Human Brain Project, <https://humanbrainproject.eu/>

⁶EBRAINS, <https://ebrains.eu/>

⁷ICE4HPC, <https://www.e4company.com/en/ice4hpc/>

Fig. 2: InterActive Computing service implementation at Cineca

applied to GPUs, which are, on the contrary, allocated exclusively.

The choice of a Jupyter-based framework for the IAC implementation brought several advantages. Firstly, it already includes a server-client approach (Jupyter Single-user) among its possible implementations. Secondly, it includes a plugin system which allowed us to extend the interface to better address the HPC capabilities (e.g. monitoring tools, jupyter-server-proxy plugin to proxy additional http-based servers through Jupyter dashboard). Lastly, it is a well-known environment for many users who approach an HPC environment for the first time, allowing a more user-friendly impact with the infrastructure.

The security of the service is strongly improved by the fact that all the operations which might be critical to run on the HPC cluster are delegated to a VM running on Cineca cloud infrastructure. The backend part running on the HPC cluster does not need root privileges, and it works like an ordinary SLURM job in user space. In addition, user login is enforced via 2FA authentication, and constant monitoring of potential security issues, as well as periodic vulnerability assessments and penetration tests (VAPT), are currently performed.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Integrating the VisIVO kernel into the InterActive Computing service simplifies user workflow, eliminating the need for manual module loading. Previously, users logging into the Galileo 100 (G100) cluster had to rely on *ssh* and command line interface to enable VisIVO functionalities. Still, with such an approach the generated PNG files were not easily accessible within the cluster. On the other hand, in the alternative approach we tested in this work, we created a dedicated Jupyter kernel for VisIVO inside the InterActive Computing interface. The VisIVO kernel is now pre-configured, allowing users to log into the InterActive Computing service and select the VisIVO kernel, which automatically loads the VisIVO module. It enables seamless execution of VisIVO commands without additional configuration, ensuring that all generated PNG files are instantly visible within the web interface. The integration simplifies the process and enhances efficiency, allowing users

to focus on their scientific visualization tasks without dealing with command-line complexities.

A. VisIVO wrappers

VisIVO is implemented in C/C++; thus, its compilation provides binary executables. Jupyter does not provide a way to integrate binary executables in its interface, whereas it provides out-of-the-box support for adding interaction with custom Python environments. Thus, we implemented a Python wrapper⁸ to connect Python and the compiled VisIVO binaries to execute VisIVO commands within a Python environment.

We rely mainly on the standard library from Python; in particular, in this work we used the *subprocess* package to run the underlying VisIVO commands. The idea is to keep track of all the details of the executions via the *logging* package, which is also important in view of the future developments [9] we are planning (see Section VI).

The Python wrapper program organizes functions to manage the three main VisIVO commands: VisIVOImporter, VisIVOFiler, and VisIVOViewer. This structure ensures that each function focuses on a specific command covering the common capabilities of running CLI commands, keeping track of the logging, and matching the functions' arguments with the allowed options of the underlying command. The above three functions are organized as follows (just importer is shown here below as an example): the options from the VisIVOImporter binary are converted as arguments of the function:

```
python
def importer(input_file, *flags, mpi=False, tasks=
None, fformat=None, out=None, volume=None,
compz=None, [...]):
```

and after that each of them has been processed to check the variable type, via an options dictionary:

```
python
options = {
    "fformat": (fformat, str),
    "out": (out, str),
    "volume": (volume, str),
    "compz": (compz, float),
    "compy": (compy, float),
    "compz": (compz, float),
    "sizex": (sizex, float),
    [...]
```

Such dictionary is passed to a function which is in charge to pipe such options to the VisIVO commands:

```
python
command = "VisIVOImporter"
_corefunction(command, input_file, *flags, mpi=mpi
, tasks=tasks, options=options)
```

⁸VisIVO Python Wrapper: <https://github.com/VisIVOLab/VisIVOPythonWrapper>

We preferred such approach to other more compact possibilities because we choose to hide as much as possible the VisIVO CLI in the background to the user, and thus we preferred to list all the possible options in the function arguments, instead of embedding them in a single optional list of tuples.

The main steps of the `_corefunction` are the following: first it checks the type of the options values passed from the outer function:

```
python
worked_options = {}
if options:
    for key, (val, expected_type) in options.items():
        if val is not None:
            if not isinstance(val, expected_type):
                raise TypeError(f"'{key}' must be of type {expected_type.__name__}")
            if expected_type is bool:
                if val: # add only if True
                    worked_options[key] = val
            else:
                worked_options[key] = val
```

Then, it converts the boolean variables into options without values, and the other ones into options with values:

```
python
for option, value in worked_options.items():
    if isinstance(value, (list, tuple)):
        command.append(f"--{option}")
        command.extend(map(str, value))
    elif value and type(value) != bool:
        command.append(f"--{option}")
        command.append(str(value))
    else:
        if value != False:
            command.append(f"--{option}")
```

Finally, the VisIVO command to be run is completed adding the input file:

```
python
command.append(input_file)
```

Such a command is run either via MPI or serially, depending if the variables `mpi` and `tasks` are set or not:

```
python
if mpi:
    mpi_command = ["mpirun", "-n", str(tasks)] + command
    logging.debug(f"Running MPI command: {mpi_command}")
    result = subprocess.run(mpi_command, capture_output=True, text=True)
else:
    logging.debug(f"Running command: {command}")
    result = subprocess.run(command, capture_output=True, text=True)
```

Other minor portions of codes are here skipped for the sake of brevity.

VisIVO kernel integrates the *Pillow* module to improve image visualization efficiency, especially for PNG files. Viewing images directly from the command line can be time-consuming, often requiring external tools or manual file opening. By incorporating *Pillow*, users can display images seamlessly within the VisIVO Python environment, eliminating the need for additional steps. This enhancement significantly speeds up the workflow and provides the convenience of immediate image rendering within Jupyter notebooks, making analyzing graphical output easier.

B. Deployment

The environment creation involves four steps:

- 1) Spack module compilation for VisIVO
- 2) *conda* environment creation via *Ansible* on the IAC backend nodes
- 3) installation of the Python wrappers from the GitHub repository
- 4) customization of *ipykernel*.

The first step involves a system-wide installation of VisIVO, compiling it via Spack [10]. A Spack module was created forcing OSMesa interface in all the graphical dependencies (notably VTK and Glew). This is a crucial step to let the IAC service correctly generate the images to be displayed, since there is no windowing system active on the IAC service (only the web interface is up and running) and thus an off-screen rendering is needed.

After this step, a *conda* environment is created via *Ansible* [11]. Inside this, the Python wrappers described in Section IV run. There is no particular need of other dependencies since the Python wrappers just rely on the Python standard library, but other Python packages were added to ease the user experience on displaying images and plots (e.g. *Pillow*, *Numpy*-based libraries, *Matplotlib*). This is where Python adds a clear advantage to the traditional VisIVO experience, since from the same environment the users can perform their data analysis relying on both the VisIVO tools and the traditional Python tools, as well as displaying the generated images on the fly via e.g. *IPython* display functionalities inside the Jupyter web interface.

Ansible playbooks deploying the VisIVO virtual environment install in parallel the software on the local storage of each one of the computational nodes involved in the Slurm partition dedicated to the IAC service. This is preferred over an installation relying on the parallel file system of the cluster since several tests we performed with the latter approach showed poor performances in the login phase of the service; this is luckily due to the poor management of large numbers of small-sized files by the parallel file system, which is the case of the multiple backend *conda* environments that has to be read by the Jupyter server initialization procedure. The deployment then relies on an *Ansible* inventory which explicitly lists all the backend nodes participating in the service, and it is executed from the login node of the system (which acts as *Ansible* controller node).

After this step, the ipykernel interface which initializes the VisIVO kernel inside the Jupyter interface is modified to run a bash prolog, which allows to load the spack module containing the VisIVO installation and to set the environment variables it needs.

V. USE CASE APPLICATIONS

A. Workflows description

In this section we demonstrate the integration of the VisIVO Server with the IAC through the three sample workflows described in [12] and briefly reported hereafter.

1) *Workflow 1*: The first workflow imports a sample TXT file containing cosmological particles' positions employing the following command:

```
bash
VisIVOImporter --fformat ascii clusterfields4.ascii
```

and visualizes it using a data points rendering:

```
bash
VisIVOViewer -x X -y Y -z Z --scale --glyphs pixel
VisIVOServerBinary.bin
```

2) *Workflow 2*: The second workflow imports a sample snapshot of a cosmological simulation in GADGET format containing cosmological particles' positions of the GAS, HALO and STARS. The importing of the simulation is executed using MPI/OpenMP because the VisIVO GADGET importer has been recently implemented to be run of HPC infrastructures scaling on multi-nodes and multi-cores when available. This is a sample command when running on 2 cores and 4 nodes:

```
bash
export OMP_NUM_THREADS=2
mpirun --np 4 VisIVOImporter --fformat gadget --out
NewTable --file snapdir/snap_091.0
```

The HALO particles in VBT format are then filtered to compute the particle densities using the *pointproperty* filter on a 64X64X64 resolution.

```
bash
VisIVOFilter --op pointproperty --resolution 64 64 64 --
points POS_X POS_Y POS_Z --append --outcol density --
file NewTableHALO.bin
```

Finally, we visualize the HALO particles using a data point rendering and the density field for the color palette.

```
bash
VisIVOViewer --x POS_X --y POS_Y --z POS_Z --color --
colorscalar density --colortable volren_glow --
logscale --out VisIVOServerImage NewTableHALO.bin
```


Fig. 3: Jupyter notebook running VisIVO via web browser on a compute node of Galileo 100 cluster

3) *Workflow 3*: The third workflow employs the same sample snapshot of the cosmological simulation imported in the workflow reported in Section V-A2 but, differently from Workflow 2, it creates a volume from the particles position using the *pointdistribute* filter which produces a density field distributed and divided for the volume voxels.

```
bash
VisIVOFilter --op pointdistribute --resolution 64 64 64 --
points POS_X POS_Y POS_Z --out densityvolume.bin --
file NewTableHALO.bin
```

The final volume is then visualized using a volume rendering algorithm.

```
bash
VisIVOViewer --volume --vrendering --vrenderingfield
Constant --color --colortable volren_glow --showlut
--out img --file densityvolume.bin
```

B. Interactive Notebooks and Rendering results

The VisIVO module is available to be launched as a Notebook or Console environment, see Figure 3.

The interactive notebooks require the VisIVO wrappers module to be loaded.

```
python
import visivo
```

1) *Workflow 1 notebook*: The first workflow is implemented using the following commands:

```
python
visivo.importer("clusterfields4.ascii", fformat
="ascii")
visivo.viewer("VisIVOServerBinary.bin", x="X",
y="Y", z="Z", scale=True, glyphs="pixel")
```

2) *Workflow 2 notebook*: We implemented the notebook for the second workflow by using the following commands:

```
python
visivo.importer("snapdir/snap_091.0", fformat="
gadget", out="NewTable", mpi=True, tasks=4)
visivo.filter("NewTableHALO.bin", op="
pointproperty", resolution="64_64_64", points="
POS_X_POS_Y_POS_Z", append=True, outcol="
density")
visivo.viewer("NewTableHALO.bin", x="POS_X", y=
"POS_Y", z="POS_Z", color=True, colorscalar="
density", colortable="volren_glow", logscale=
True, out="VisIVOServerImage")
```

In this second notebook we can test the capability to execute the importer command using MPI with 4 processes.

3) *Workflow 3 notebook*: The notebook for the third workflow executes the following commands:

```
python
visivo.importer("snapdir/snap_091.0", fformat="
gadget", out="NewTable", mpi=True, tasks=4)
visivo.filter("NewTableHALO.bin", op="
pointdistribute", resolution="64_64_64", points=
"POS_X_POS_Y_POS_Z", out="densityvolume.bin")
visivo.viewer("densityvolume.bin", volume=True,
vrendering=True, vrenderingfield="Constant",
color=True, colortable="volren_glow", showlut=
True, out="img")
```

Figure 4 shows the rendering results of the GADGET snapshots used in workflows 2 and 3. It presents a volume rendering of the density of GADGET's HALO particles.

Fig. 4: VisIVO volume rendering of HALO particles of GADGET simulation test output

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper presented the innovative incorporation of VisIVO into the InterActive Computing service to allow interactive analyses and visualizations abstracting the underlying large-scale HPC resources.

This activity comprised the implementation of Python wrappers that will be further used in future works to expand the development toward different directions. The integration with Jupyter can be extended to enrich the functionalities or by

adding customized functions which were not present in the native command line VisIVO implementation, to exploit the interactive capabilities at most. For instance, specific functions to display images with embedded plots might be easily added relying on the wide availability of Python graphical tools. Another possible development which still exploits the functions-based structure and avoids once again the need of a VisIVO local installation might be to utilize a REST API built via Flask library to enable the remote execution of VisIVO on a server to expose the application's functionality through HTTP endpoints, and provide an interactive interface that abstracts the complexity of backend operations.

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